

MEDIA AND INFORMATION LITERACY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AS THE BASIS OF THE NEED FOR INFORMATION

Shermanova Feruza Djumaboyevna

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Republic of Uzbekistan

shermanovaf@gmail.com, ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0985-4793

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Abstract: In this article, students are told about information, which is the foundation of today's modern information space and is an integral part of human social and cultural life, and the desire for it, formation of media and information literacy skills, understanding and evaluation of information received in the global information space. In today's digital age, the ability to access, evaluate, and effectively utilize media and information is crucial for individuals to navigate the complexities of the modern world. This article explores the significance of media and information literacy (MIL) within the educational process as the cornerstone for developing information competency among learners. By examining the theoretical underpinnings of MIL and its practical applications in educational settings, this paper highlights the importance of integrating MIL into curriculum frameworks across disciplines. Moreover, it discusses strategies for educators to foster MIL skills, including critical thinking, digital literacy, and ethical use of information. Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature and empirical evidence, this article advocates for the prioritization of MIL education to empower learners with the necessary tools to engage with information responsibly and constructively in the digital era.

Keywords: Information competence, information literacy, media sources, UNESCO and Ifla, information security, Educational Process, Critical Thinking, Digital Literacy

1 INTRODUCTION

The history of human society reliably shows that only those inventions, discoveries and innovations that were accepted by the culture of society and became an integral part of it quickly found their practical application. The introduction of other innovations was often delayed for a long time. Therefore, the information culture of the society is the main factor of its successful information development, and it is considered as the most important condition for ensuring the country's socio-economic development and national security in the modern world.

Information competence is a necessary condition for successful socialization of a person in modern society. Today, the results of scientific and technical progress that we can observe in the advanced countries of the world community show that the conditions of daily life and professional activity of millions of people on our planet, including in Uzbekistan, have passed the first decade of the 21st century. It is completely different from the conditions in which we lived and worked at the end of the century. And these differences are mainly related to the revolutionary changes in the information environment of society, the rapid development of new informatics and information technologies and their penetration into all other spheres of society: economy, science, education, politics and culture. Therefore, information competence is becoming a necessary condition for successful socialization of a person in the new information environment of society today. Previously, this condition should be applied not to all members of society, but only to those who prepare themselves for professional activity in the information field.

The proliferation of digital technologies has transformed the way information is created, disseminated, and consumed, revolutionizing various aspects of society, including education. In this digital age, individuals are inundated with a vast array of media content and information sources, ranging from traditional print media to online platforms and social networks. While this unprecedented access to information presents numerous opportunities, it also poses challenges, particularly regarding the ability to discern credible sources, analyze complex messages, and navigate the ever-expanding digital landscape.

Media and information literacy (MIL) has emerged as a fundamental competency in navigating this information-rich environment. MIL encompasses the skills, knowledge, and attitudes necessary for individuals to access, understand, evaluate, and create media and information effectively. It empowers learners to critically engage with various forms of media, discern bias and misinformation, and communicate ideas ethically and responsibly. As such, integrating MIL into the educational process is essential for equipping learners with the competencies required to thrive in the 21st century.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In our country, systematic work has been carried out for many years to create the social and legal foundations of the information society. In particular, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of June 6, 2002 "On further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies"[1] have been adopted. At the same time, the decision of our Resident on June 30, 2017 No. RQ-5099 "On measures

to fundamentally improve the conditions for the development of information technologies in the Republic" [2] is evidence of this. Also, Appendix 3 of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 187 of April 6, 2017 "On approval of state educational standards of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education", Paragraph 4, which is one of the basic competences, "Competence of working with information - refers to the ability to find, sort, process, store and effectively use the necessary information from media sources, ensure their safety, and develop the ability to acquire media culture. holds" [3]. At its core, MIL draws upon interdisciplinary perspectives, including communication studies, education, psychology, and information science. Drawing from concepts such as critical literacy, digital literacy, and information literacy, MIL emphasizes the development of cognitive, affective, and behavioral competencies that enable individuals to engage with media and information critically and reflexively.

Critical thinking lies at the heart of MIL, enabling individuals to question assumptions, evaluate evidence, and make informed judgments about media messages and information sources. By fostering critical thinking skills, MIL empowers learners to interrogate the credibility and reliability of information, recognize bias and propaganda, and resist manipulation and misinformation.

Digital literacy is another key component of MIL, encompassing the ability to navigate digital technologies effectively, evaluate online resources, and participate in digital communities responsibly. In an increasingly interconnected world, digital literacy skills are essential for individuals to communicate, collaborate, and create content across various online platforms.

Information literacy complements MIL by focusing on the skills needed to locate, evaluate, and use information effectively to solve problems and make informed decisions. Information literacy skills include the ability to identify information needs, formulate research questions, search for relevant sources, critically evaluate information, and synthesize findings into coherent arguments. Information literacy includes the following skills:

- ✓ Determining / understanding your information needs: What do I need? What problem am I trying to solve?
- ✓ Identification of information sources: Which information sources should be used:
Internet information, books or TV.
- ✓ Which of the following sources should be used:
primary, secondary or tertiary?
- Searching for information: Where should I look for information? Who should I turn to for help?
- ✓ Analyzing the quality of information and evaluating it: determining the reliability and truthfulness of information.

- ✓ Information organization, storage or archiving: how to effectively organize information from multiple information sources?

- ✓ Effective use of information in compliance with ethical norms: what should be done so that the copyright of information creators is not violated?

- ✓ Creation and exchange of new knowledge: How can information be presented? [4]

Below, the level of influence of these factors on the development of medical literacy of students will be discussed.

- ✓ Content of social environment (macro and micro environment).

- ✓ Family education.

- ✓ Activities of educational institutions.

- ✓ The influence of parents, pedagogues, responsible persons and peers.

- ✓ Student's personal approach and spiritual and moral values.

- ✓ The role of media in the student's life and its impact on his personality.

Below we will talk about pedagogical activities and their possibilities, which are organized in forms that are considered effective in organizing media education of a well-rounded person in an information society:

- The lesson of mastering new knowledge. (mainly in lectures)
- The lesson of strengthening knowledge and formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities. (in lectures and seminar classes)
- Generalization and systematization of knowledge (in lectures and seminar classes)
- Knowledge, skills, skills control and knowledge correction lesson (in lectures and seminar classes)

3 ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Information literacy is related to the conscious formation and development of interpersonal skills regardless of the technologies used in the information space. The problem of preparing a person to live in an information society through information is traditionally the focus of the international community and, first of all, international organizations. UNESCO supports the development of media and information literacy and considers it "the basis for building an inclusive, open, participatory and pluralistic knowledge society." In connection with the growing impact of mass media and information technologies on people's lives, preparation of people to live in the information society has appeared as an urgent problem before the international community. The solution to these problems is found globally in UNESCO and IFLA (International Federation of Library AssociationC) documents, including the Grunwald Declaration on Media Education (1982), the Alexandria Declaration on Information Literacy and Lifelong Learning. (2005), "Paris program and 12 recommendations on media education" (2007) are expressed in the documents.

The term "Information literacy" was first used in 1974 in a report written by the President of the Software and Information Industry Association, Paul Zurkovski, on behalf of the National Commission on Libraries and Informatics. Zurkovski used this phrase to refer to people who are information literate, who have the opportunity to use a wide range of media in addition to primary sources in solving their problems, and their specific techniques and skills. [5]

Foreign scientists such as A. Amacdo, Adam Swinyard, Niall Marriott, J. D. Willms, T. V. Malon, I. Kh. Fushc, etc., works on modern information technologies and their classification, CIS scientists A. I. Berg, V. M. Bryabrin, A. R. Esayan, V. Makarova, Ye. I. Mashbis, A. Miklyaev, V. I. Strajev, A. Faysman, etc., have works related to the introduction of information and communication technologies in education.

In Uzbekistan, preliminary studies on the implementation of information technologies in education were carried out in the doctoral dissertation of A. Abdukadirov "Theory and practice of intensive training of teachers of physics and mathematics: aspects of the use of computer technologies in the educational process". According to the professor, the application of information technologies to the educational process increases the efficiency and quality of education, as well as its speed several times [6].

U. Begimkulov in his doctoral dissertation on the topic "Theory and practice of organization and management of informatization of pedagogical educational processes" recognizes that the use of information technologies in educational management ensures the achievement of effective results [7].

In the research work of O. Davlatov entitled "Development of students' competence to ensure information security through the means of historical and cultural heritage", "Ensuring information security is, first of all, the analysis, evaluation and detection of harmful information from various information sources, protecting students from the threat of harmful information. It is concluded that "protecting oneself and members of society requires preparing to fight against them" [8].

D. Abduazimova and the team of authors published "Instructions on ensuring children's information security in the context of the globalization of telecommunication systems" and recommendations on protecting children from information distributed on the Internet and mass media [9].

H. Dostmuhammad gave the following points about information literacy in his work entitled "Democratic models of mass media development". "Accepting the given information directly leads to problems like accepting any given food. But we cannot develop without a unified information space. In addition, a famous saying "Discovered in the age of information" says that "in a society where information is slow, thinking is also slow work" [10].

Regardless of what we call it, it is true that the skill of avoiding information has appeared in the conditions

of globalization. "According to economist Herbert Simon, winner of the Nobel Prize, currently information is killing and eating its consumers (recipients)" [11].

In such conditions, not only journalists are required to enjoy information, to use information correctly, to distinguish right from wrong, but also to be able to receive information, process and distribute it, and create text in the news society.

4 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the course of the research, it was found that the use of the following types and forms of the lesson helps to effectively develop students' media and information literacy:

1. Acquisition of new knowledge (form: lecture, presentation).

2. The lesson of strengthening knowledge and formation of knowledge, skills, skills (in the form of: discussion, training, laboratory work, project, report, case, games - intellectual and role-playing games).

3. Lesson of generalization and systematization of knowledge (form: seminar, presentation, competition, examination - quiz).

4. Knowledge, skills, skills control and knowledge correction lesson (in the form of: case study, written work, essay, test, exam).

5. Mixed class (in the form of a roundtable discussion, interview, excursion, conference, seminar, "Skills class", practical exercises on a computer).

As an experiment in the development of students' information and media literacy, practical lessons were organized on the following topics:

1. "Media products: how to use them effectively?" Media competence of the pedagogue in the educational process, presentation of the interview.

2. "Using modern practical programs in media text preparation."

3. Mobile phones. Preparation of content on the topic of the influence of virtual games on the minds of young people.

4. "Preparation of electronic materials related to the educational process using mobile applications."

5. "Creating a small project promoting information culture in the media field."

Control of knowledge, skills, skills and correction of knowledge is more effective mainly in practical lessons. The fundamentals of media education acquired by the students, the knowledge of the structural elements of media and information literacy, the ability to put them into practice, the control of their skills, and the correction of knowledge were directed. Case, written work, essay, trial, test, exam are the most popular forms in this lesson. The use of cases in the educational process is convenient for connecting theoretical knowledge with practice, especially in the formation of information search, analysis and evaluation skills, and effectively develops media literacy, media knowledge, media competence and media literacy in students.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the theoretical analysis show that in modern society, every person is at the center of the

media environment, regardless of his will. Today, every person uses the information distributed through the media as a source of information, communication, information transfer, self-development, education and recreation, ability demonstration, and communication tool in the process of organizing personal and professional activities.

Research on information literacy shows that, despite the fact that technological skills and media and information literacy are considered to be better developed among young people, today's students face certain difficulties in assessing the reliability of information even during the educational process. In this case, the information disseminated through the media is intended to satisfy the vital needs of a person such as obtaining information, transmitting information, storing information, communicating, establishing communication, self-development, education and recreation, demonstrating personal abilities, and fulfilling such goals. In this case, the information disseminated through the media is intended to satisfy the vital needs of a person such as obtaining information, transmitting information, storing information, communicating, establishing communication, self-development, education and recreation, demonstrating personal abilities and fulfilling such goals. The development of the media and information competence of the pedagogue is considered one of the most urgent problems in the professional field of understanding, evaluating and forming critical thinking of the information received in the global information space. It also opens the door to a wide range of opportunities for enriching the educational environment and increasing activity in the teaching and learning process.

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